

The Effects of Static Electricity of a Dead Fly

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Introduction

Despite being a ubiquitous phenomenon, electrostatic charge remains poorly understood. The occurrence of electrostatic charges has been described on a wide range of artificial and natural surfaces, including contact between such natural sources as ash particles in a volcanic eruption, clouds and the ground resulting in lightning, and moving water. Static electricity is also produced by organisms during movement, such as the flight of honeybees that generate sufficient charges to attract neutral pollen particles and aid in plant pollination. Besides these naturally occurring sources of electrostatic charges, such fields can also be artificially induced through friction between materials, with electron transfer in a process termed triboelectric charging. These charges are associated with static electromagnetic fields whose interaction exerts a physical force that results in the attraction or repulsion of charged objects brought close to each other. The current report details these mechanical effects of static electric fields as observed following the exposure of a dead fly (*Drosophila melanogaster*) to artificially generated static charges on a copper plate and the experimenter's finger.

Materials

- Wimshurst static machine
- Laboratory flies (*Drosophila melanogaster*) from Carolina Biological Supply Company
- Copper sheet
- Working bench and shelf

Procedure

The flies used in the experiment were *Drosophila melanogaster* virgin females, which were supplied in vials by the Carolina Biological Supply Company. After being received, one vial of the flies was left on a working shelf, resulting in the flies dying naturally. One fly was then placed on a copper sheet charged with the Wimshurst static machine. The experimenter's finger was then brought close to the fly on the copper plate several times.

Results

On bringing a finger close to the fly on the charged copper plate, the fly's body was noted to move upwards toward the finger. Upon touching the finger, the dead fly immediately dropped back onto the charged copper plate before bouncing upwards towards the finger overhead. These movements occurred repeatedly for as long as the finger was held close to the fly's body. In addition, the speed of movement of the fly from the sheet to the finger decreased with increasing distance to the overhead finger, ceasing completely once the finger was moved beyond a certain distance away from the sheet. However, the speed with which the body bounced between the finger and the charge copper sheet was not attenuated over time, provided that the finger was within the critical distance for the movement to occur. The results are accessible on YouTube: <https://youtu.be/x2pgD3zLNqA>

Discussion

The observed movement of the dead fly's body between the charged copper plate and the experimenter's finger can be explained in terms of static charge transfer between the surfaces involved. To understand this behavior, two concepts in electrostatic charges must be understood: charge transfer and attraction or repulsion between charged surfaces.

Conventionally, electrostatic charges can be transferred through friction, direct contact, or induction. The most commonly observed sources of electrostatic charges are acquired through friction, with objects or surfaces being rubbed against each other to produce opposite

charges that cause the objects to attract. In this case, electron transfer to an accepting object, usually plastic materials, from a donor object such as a cloth results in a negatively charged surface (plastic) and a positively charged surface (cloth). Conversely, electrostatic charges can be transferred through conduction, in which case the two objects gain the same type of charge. For instance, a positively charged metallic rod can transfer the positive electrostatic charge to a piece of paper placed in direct contact with it. A third form of electrostatic charge transfer is through induction, which results in formation of an opposite charge that reverses upon removal of the inducing source ((Heinert et al. 2). For instance, a positively charged object brought close to a neutral object attracts electrons to the surface of the neutral object closest to it, inducing a negative charge on this pole and resulting in the two objects attracting each other. If brought close to each other, charged surfaces can either attract or repel each other, an effect induced by the electromagnetic force associated with positive and negative charges. Conventionally, similarly charged bodies repel each other, while oppositely charged surfaces attract each other due to the opposite polarities of the electromagnetic fields generated by the two different charges. In the current experiment, the combination of repetitive charge accumulation and loss by the fly's body through conduction, as well as by the finger through induction, resulted in the observed bizarre bouncing between the two surfaces.

In the experiment, a series of steps of electrostatic charge transfers and concurrent attractive and repulsive forces acting on the fly's body account for the observed effects. First, the copper sheet is positively charged by the Wimhurst machine. Second, on coming into contact with the copper sheet, the fly acquires a similar negative charge through conduction. Third, upon being hovered over the positively charged copper sheet (with the fly on it), the experimenter's finger acquires a negative charge through induction, in which electrons are attracted to the finger's surface closest to the positively charged sheet. The resultant

electromagnetic field causes attraction between the copper sheet (including the similarly charged fly's body on it) and the finger. However, since the copper sheet is too heavy to move toward the finger (or vice versa), only the fly's body bounces toward the finger. The fourth event occurs once the fly's body comes into contact with the finger, with the negative electrodes flowing into it by conduction and converting the fly's charge from positive to negative. Immediately following this event, the fly's body (now bearing a negative charge) is attracted back onto the positively charged copper sheet, towards which it bounces. Upon hitting the copper sheet, the fly gains a positive charge, and the cycle is repeated. Therefore, the observed oscillation of the dead fly's body between the copper sheet and the experimenter's finger is the result of a rapid transfer of electrostatic charges with associated attractive and repulsive electromagnetic forces.

Conclusion

Electrostatic charges can be generated through different natural and artificial processes. In the current experiment, the generation and transfer of static charges between a copper sheet, a dead fly's body, and the experimenter's finger is discussed. The rapid transfer of charges through both conduction and induction resulted in the observed oscillation of the dead fly's body between the copper sheet and the finger. This experiment highlights the potential effect of static electricity on the bodies of small insects, which can be the basis of unusual behavioral patterns in environments with high amounts of static electricity.

Work Cited

Heinert, Carter, et al. "Electrostatic Charge Generation on Material Surfaces from the Evaporation of Liquids." *Journal of Electrostatics*, vol. 105, 2020, p. 1-19, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ELSTAT.2020.103450>.